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**ПСИХОЛІНГВІСТИЧНІ АСПЕКТИ СПРИЙНЯТТЯ
АНГЛОАМЕРИКАНІЗМІВ НОСІЯМИ УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ МОВИ**
*Psycholinguistic Aspects of Perception of Angloamericanisms by Native
Speakers of the Ukrainian Language*

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Abstract

The abstract deals with the problem of the Angloamericanisms perception by the Ukrainian speakers. The ways of loan adaptation have been shown. The Angloamericanisms have been characterized according to the psycholinguistic procedure of language associations on the basis of associative experiment with 100 reviewed informants. An experimental list consists of twenty words related to the most frequent thematic subsystems in the adopting language: business, economy, entertainments, sport and fashion. The types of psychological components identification are characterized. The comparable analysis of results has proved that the assimilation of the loans is high enough. However, the respondents demonstrated the large creativity in determination of semantics and in presentation of associative reactions on the loans, which testify to aspiration to show their linguistic abilities.

Key words: *angloamericanism, associative experiment, assimilation, loan, psycholinguistics.*

Introduction

The changing world reality motivates changing perceptions, which leads to the changing mission of language and communication scholars. This area of study is no longer the study of language diffusion or distribution, but the study of language of mobility (Li Chaoyuan, 2016).

The relevance of the study is the problems of borrowing foreign vocabulary, its further adaptation due to a number of linguistic reasons. Interlingual reasons are associated with the massive nature of the use of foreign-language innovations and

their active participation in many language processes observed by the Ukrainian language.

The interest of linguists in the study of this area is based on the insufficient knowledge of some aspects of the linguistic phenomenon of borrowing and the accompanying processes of adaptation of foreign words.

Even so, the important point remains that speakers use some vocabulary only in some situations and not in others. Perhaps a context-dependent adjustment of relative language activation could be arranged via the task/decision system (Dijkstra, Wahl, Buytenhuijs, Vanhalem, Al-jibouri, de Korte & Rekké, 2018: 3).

Methods and Techniques of the Research

Associative experiment is used in various fields of knowledge: linguistics, psychology, sociology, and others. The use of this method varies depending on the purpose and objectives of a particular science.

Free associative experiment is a rather simple and at the same time an effective means of research in psycholinguistics. He provides the material for building associative fields of certain concepts, reconstruction of fragments of language and conceptual pictures of the world (Hsin-Yi Liang & Kelsen, 2018: 760). Studies on the brink of scientific disciplines are held for a relatively short time, they have intensified in world science in the second half of the past, and especially in the current century. In recent years, intelligence in psycho- and sociolinguistics has revived in Ukraine ([Lydiah Kananu Kiramba, 2018: 300](#)).

Our study preferred the written form of an experiment that has certain time constraints and contributes to the discovery of spontaneous associations, while in writing there are factors that complicate spontaneous responsiveness.

The individual form enables to record the response time and deprives other people of the respondent's response. One of the most complex and under-researched problems of carrying out an associative experiment is the creation of a stimulus list.

The relevance of the chosen topic is also justified by the insufficient study of the latest modern borrowings from the point of view of their perception by native speakers of the recipient language.

In connection with the above provisions, the purpose of the study was determined – the study of the perception of the latest Angloamericanisms by native speakers of the Ukrainian language.

This goal led to the formulation of the following tasks:

- 1) to identify the features of the perception of borrowed;
- 2) to highlight the main associations;
- 3) to characterize the types of psychological components identification.

The object of research is lexical borrowing.

The subject of this work is the nature and mechanisms of mastering foreign vocabulary by the system of the recipient language and its native speakers.

Two group of Ukrainian recipients took part in the experiment aged 17–19 years.

The choice of the age group is not accidental. The representatives are people who use the Angloamericanisms more often. They have a well-formed vocabulary and an active social position. In addition, the representatives of each group perceived the borrowed vocabulary under conditions of limiting the knowledge base, who were not working in special fields and unfamiliar with the realities of foreign life.

The total number of informants was 100 native speakers of the Ukrainian language.

The subjects were asked to complete the following tasks:

1. to write down the subjective definition of each word;
2. to give the associations for each loan.

Due to the large volume of material, the list of words proposed to different group included 20 units borrowed in the Ukrainian language that relate to different areas of society: economy, computer technology, culture, sports, and everyday life. Words were presented in isolation, out of any context: *кашерінг, флаєр, релакс, дисконт, драйв, лузер, екшн, кул, роумінг, провайдер, принт, топлес, дайвінг, рекрутинг, кліринг, трафік, банер, скріншот, сейл, стартап.*

Results

In the first task, informants were asked to indicate the meaning of the borrowed words. An analysis of the obtained explications made it possible to identify that most of the informants have given appropriate definitions.

The analysis of the results of the first task made it possible to evaluate the words under study by the novelty parameter.

Table 1. *The degree of the novelty of the loans*

Loan	The degree of novelty %	Loan	The degree of novelty %	Loan	The degree of novelty %
кашерінг	15	роумінг	0	банер	5
флаєр	0	провайдер	0	скрнішот	0
релакс	0	принт	3	сейл	2
дисконт	0	топлес	5	стартап	3
драйв	0	дайвінг	0		
Лузер	0	рекрутингр	10		
Екшн	0	клінінг	3		
Кул	0	трафік	5		

The results of the analysis of the semantic description showed that the perception of borrowed words is due to the age characteristics of the carriers and the nature of the lexical units themselves. Below are the main strategies for identifying the meanings of foreign vocabulary, typical for recipients of the studied groups according to the identification of the meaning of lexical borrowings:

a) associative strategy: *флаєр – знижка*;

b) strategy based on the similarity of the sound-graphic design of foreign words: *драйв – кайф*;

c) the strategy of resorting to a foreign language prototype, which is used in cases where the presented foreign language word is not familiar to them or in cases where it is necessary to clarify its meaning: *трафік – дорожній рух, екшн – дія*.

The importance of the second task is to identify the ability of informants to independently choose associations for borrowed words.

The result of the experiment was 2600 reactions.

So there is the analysis of the most widespread associations connected with the Angloamericanisms (see Table 2).

In the analysis of associations of respondents for Angloamericanisms, it was discovered that not always the reaction to a word that correlates with its vocabulary may mean its correct interpretation, as confirmed by 60% of students.

Table 2. The loan associations

Loan	The most widespread associations connected with the meaning	The most widespread associations not connected with the meaning
Кашерінг	Автомобіль, дорога	Спорт, кашель, одяг, кашемір, гроші, готівка
Флаєр	Листок, реклама, оголошення, бумага, буклет, роздавати	
Релакс	Пляж, диван, спа, відпочинок, медитація, сон, спиртне, масаж, задоволення	
Дисконт	Знижка, рахунок, картка, гроші, акція	Заборона, заперечення, дискусія
Драйв	Енергія, адреналін, відчуття, перегони, запалювати, дискотека, насолода, весело, швидкість, кайф	
Лузєр	Невдаха, лох, лопух, ніччєма, ботан	
Єкшн	Фільм, кіно, жанр, емоції, нїмоврно, Сїльвєстр Сталонє	Автомат, акція
Кул	Круто, крутий	
Роумїнг	Розповсюдження, МТС, Vodafone, доступ, соцмережа, з'єднання	Реклама, ринг тон
Проваїдер	Забезпечення, дати доступ, Інтернет, кабель, роздавати, Шторм, Воля	Новинка
Прїнт	1. Малюнок, друк, футболка, одяг, квітка, візерунок, модно. 2. Принтер, друкувати	
Топлес	Бєз одягу, голий, фотосєсія, оголенє тїло, морє, пляж	Каблук, нє в топї, бєз верхнього одягу
Дайвінг	Плавання, спорт, вода, занурення, морє, океан	
Рєкрутїнг	Робїтник, підбїр кадрїв, бїзнєс	Бандит, рєкрут
Клінінг	Чисто, кімната, прибирання, прибирати, Mr Proper, прибиральниця	Клініка
Трафік	1. Мегабайти, Інтернет, обмеження. 2. Затор, дорога, машина, аварія	
Банєр	Реклама, інформація, вивїска, стєнд	Баня
Скрїншот	Збереженє фото, галєрея, телефон, фото екрана	
Сєйл	Акція, розпродаж, одяг, продавати, магазин	
Стартап	1. Бїзнєс, молодь, початок, старт. 2. Смішно, виступ.	

Identification of the psychological components of familiar foreign words:

- a) attribution to the situation: *трафік – обмеження доступу в Інтернеті, кул – крутий*;
- b) identification through definition: *екшн – жанр фільму*;
- c) categorization: *банер – реклама, роумінг – мобільний зв'язок*;
- d) illustrative example: *провайдер – Шторм, Воля; екшн – Сільвестр Сталоне, клінінг – Mr Proper*;
- e) synonym selection: *лузер – невдаха*;
- f) emotional-evaluative strategy, which is characterized by the presence of a subjective-emotional component: *принт (на одязі) – модно*;
- g) consonanted images: *рекрутинг – рекрут, банер – баня*.

Conclusions

Language reflects a certain way of perceiving and structure of the world, and an individual, perceiving a foreign language word, can rely on a subjective attitude to an object or phenomenon designated by it (Stig HJjarvard, 2003: 80).

The native speakers of Ukrainian have given many associations for every borrowing. In view of this fact, we can say that Angloamericanisms are used in the Ukrainian language.

Some English words had several meanings that came into the Ukrainian language. 18 percent of the respondents identified these meanings and submitted the relevant associations to them.

23% of students who did not know the meaning of English borrowing were found in the survey. Therefore, the degree of novelty of Angloamericanisms is low. 90 percent of respondents submitted associations for borrowings that were related to their meanings. Some respondents even found several meanings of borrowing. The analysis of the results of the psycholinguistic experiment shows that English borrowings have a high adaptation in the Ukrainian language. According to the number of associations for the Angloamericanisms it can be admitted that the speakers of the Ukrainian language use them in their speech which is connected with the internationalization of English in the world.

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